

Looking Seriously at Improvisational Comedians*

An Existential-Phenomenological Analysis

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Abstract

For all their ability to make us laugh, many comedians report severe struggles with mental health. Even so, this reality does not deter a growing number of improvisational (improv) comedians from endorsing applications of their craft in wellbeing-oriented workshops for the public, which claim to leverage the beneficial side effects of learning improv comedy to help with a growing list of psychological ailments like social anxiety and autism. This existential-phenomenological study explored the complex dynamics of wellbeing among eight professional improvisers (five men and three women) to illuminate the psychological vulnerabilities and resiliencies of this unique subset of the comedy community. Qualitative analysis yielded six common themes that conveyed the beneficial personal “by-products” of doing improv, which included the opportunity for adults to play, the joy of collaborative relationships, increased comfort with risk, improved confidence, a focus on positivity, and a revitalizing effect on emotional health, self-image, and sense of purpose. Stressors unique to the business aspect of improv, but not improv itself, were also revealed. Results provide valuable insights both for improvisers and those interested in the application of improv in clinical settings.

keywords: improv comedy, wellbeing, existential-phenomenology

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Introduction

Psychology to date has not afforded a dedicated literature to the study of comedians. The subject has not been entirely neglected in psychological research, but the psychology of comedians has been approached quite rarely as an end in itself. Greengross and Miller (2009) suggest that this may reflect a researcher bias toward more ‘serious’ forms of creativity—the actor (Nettle, 2006), musician (Bengtsson, Csikszentmihályi, & Ullén, 2007; Limb & Braun, 2008; Liu, et al., 2012; Villarreal, et al., 2013), visual artist (Schlegel, et al., 2015), writer (Howard-Jones, Blakemore, Samuel, Summers, & Claxton, 2005; Shah, et al., 2013; Liu, et al., 2015), and scientist (Katz, 1986; Zhang, Liu, & Zhang, 2014; Wu, Jung, & Zhang, 2016) come to mind. The last decade has seen psychologists take an increasing interest in the study of comedy, but mostly as it relates to established research focuses—creativity, humor, play, empathy, and anxiety being just a few such subjects for which comedy’s mechanism and effects have notable implications. Through these research efforts, the comedian has finally come into view as a phenomenon of inherent interest for psychology.

Precipitated by the suicide of renowned comic genius Robin Williams in 2014 at age 63, a recent pair of studies on comedians and longevity (Stewart & Thompson, 2015; Stewart, Wiley, McDermott, & Thompson, 2016) has drawn particular attention to the need for more research on mental health issues and wellbeing among comedians. Both studies found an adverse relationship between comedic ability and longevity, such that premature deaths like Williams’ might in fact be viewed as quite common among elite comedians. Stewart and Thompson (2015) note that these findings are indicative of the often paradoxical tension between comedians’ on-stage versus private personas, a tension similarly identified by Greengross and Miller (2009) and anecdotally by the great number of comedians who self-report struggles with mental health, particularly anxiety and depression. One study (Ando, Claridge, & Clark, 2014) adds that the success of elite comedians may be facilitated by certain psychotic traits in their personality structures, which might be a factor in the sexual misconduct and abuse of power for which some comedians have been exposed in recent media (Redden, 2017; Izadi, 2017; Ryzik, Buckley, & Kantor, 2017; Sims, 2017; O’Brien & Sanz, 2017). Clearly, being funny does not guarantee mental health.

Even so, a growing body of research is examining the merits of one form of comedy, improvisational (improv) comedy, as a clinical intervention for psychological disorders and vulnerable populations. The Second City comedy club in Chicago, where a long list of comedy greats including Bill Murray, Tina Fey, and Stephen Colbert got their start, is a leader in the development of these interventions with programs that leverage the mental health benefits of improv for select populations, including autism spectrum disorder and social anxiety disorder. Individuals learn to manage symptoms and problem behaviors using skills derived from improv that foster established therapeutic dimensions in the psychological literature (Sheesley, Pfeffer, & Barish, 2016): group cohesiveness (Yalom & Leszcz, 2005; Marmarosh, Holtz, & Schottenbauer, 2005), play

(Schaefer, 1993; Kedem-Tahar & Felix-Kellerman, 1996), exposure to shame (Ellis, 1987; Carretero-Dios, Ruch, Agudelo, Platt, & Proyer, 2010), and humor (Strean, 1994; Salameh & Fry, 2001; Falkenberg, Buchkremer, Bartels, & Wild, 2011; Panichelli, 2013). The Second City’s programs are based on the recognition of theoretical links between these concepts and their analogues in the fundamentals of improvised performance. But if comedians are no more exempt from mental health struggles than anyone else, how, then, can learning the fundamentals of improv be expected to increase an individual’s personal wellbeing?

Improv Comedy in Context

Improv has been defined as “any theatrical performance occurring without a script” (Sheesley, Pfeffer, & Barish, 2016, p. 158) and serves as the abbreviation for both improvisation as a skill and as a family of performance formats (i.e. improvisational theatre, improvisational comedy, Theatresports, etc.) with a shared history and mechanism. Improv, in the former sense, may be used in scripted acting and comedy (some of the most famous lines in film have been notoriously “off-script”), but such improvisations still do not qualify an otherwise scripted performance as improv in the latter sense. Performances that do qualify as such must be entirely unscripted, deriving instead from the spontaneity of the performers. Everything that happens on stage is done without planning, forethought, or rehearsal prior to the moment of its happening. To demonstrate integrity to this premise with the audience, it is conventional in improv to take audience suggestions at various points, typically as inspiration for scenes, and incorporate them into the performance. This provides the audience with the opportunity to test the performers’ purported spontaneity, which introduces an added level of risk to the performance. Working with each suggestion, rising to each challenge, is where improv derives its magic.

As an art form, improv is relatively young, having come about through innovations in storytelling and acting in twentieth century theatre. Improv games were originally developed by Viola Spolin in the 1930’s as a means for teaching theatre fundamentals to children; in this context, Spolin was also the first to use audience suggestions for inspiring scenes (Spolin, 1999; Salinsky & Frances-White, 2008). By the 1950’s, her son, Paul Sills, had joined a group of fellow young actors, the Compass Players, led by David Shepherd, and adapted Spolin’s improv games for performance onstage in Chicago. By 1960, the vision of what improv could be had grown exponentially, and Sills, Shepherd, and other members of the Compass Players had formed The Second City comedy theatre to continue growing the art form. During this period of time, improvised performance had also been taking shape at London’s Royal Court Theatre, albeit independently of events in Chicago. Prompted by his increasing dissatisfaction with the state of theatre and acting, Keith Johnstone, a new director and teacher at the Royal Court, began pioneering improv techniques with his actors in the 1950’s. He endeavored to teach the exact opposite of what he had been taught about theatre

and acting, which he viewed as having stifled his creativity (Johnstone, 1981; Salinsky & Frances-White, 2008). Johnstone soon adapted his improvisation techniques into a stageworthy performance format with which he toured across Europe before moving to Canada to teach at the University of Calgary. Here he crafted his popular competitive improv format, Theatresports, in the 1970s, before going on to found The Loose Moose comedy theatre which, like The Second City, remains highly influential in the world of improv comedy today (Salinsky & Frances-White, 2008).

It should be noted that improvised performance was not originally conceived of as a form of comedy by Spolin, Sills, Shepherd, or Johnstone. In Chicago as in London, improv first developed as a rehearsal technique for traditional theatre, and then as a performance format that had been liberated from the strictures of conventional theatre. Improv as such was never intended to produce gags and jokes—which are produced much more reliably through the conventions of scripted theatre—but rather stories that might never have taken shape beyond the moment of pure spontaneity. The discovery was only made at later stages that laughter was a remarkably consistent feature of improvised storytelling, even when gags and jokes had not presented themselves. To this end, improv today still does not always aim for comedy, in which cases it is usually referred to as improvisational theatre. But as improv’s early pioneers discovered, comedy is a clear direction toward which improv tends, and so improv comedy remains improv’s most ubiquitous form.

Since many performers have backgrounds in various combinations of acting, sketch, stand-up, and improv, the historical and formal distinctions between improv comedy and other forms of comedy do not always exist in practice, which can make it difficult to discern exactly how improv has come to fit with its cousins in theatre and comedy. Salinsky and Frances-White (2008) note that efforts to bring improv to television have mostly failed because the risk of live improvisation, felt by audience members in the immediacy of the theatre, does not translate easily to the screen.¹ As a consequence, accomplished improv comedians have not typically garnered the same kind of fame or popular media attention as stand-up and sketch comedians, which has produced the perception that improv cannot be pursued as an end in itself and thus must be a stepping-stone to supposedly more “legitimate” success in sketch and stand-up. For its part, improv comedy today continues to thrive around local theatres, and recognition in these circles remains the most direct outcome one might be interested to accomplish by learning improv.

Improv Comedy in Psychology

The perception that improv cannot be pursued as an end in itself has not proved to be exclusively negative, one particularly positive outcome being that the

¹*Whose Line Is It Anyway?* is an exception, but Salinsky and Frances-White (2008) note that the show has been criticised frequently for failing to communicate the risk felt in live performance.

indirect benefits of learning improv have received quite a bit more attention than they might otherwise have received. Improvisers have been remarkably creative in exploring these avenues and, as a result, what can be referred to as *applied improv* has become quite popular in the last decade. Principles, ideas, and techniques derived from the practice of improv have now been applied to such diverse fields as business (Vera & Crossan, 2004; Gagnon, Vough, & Nickerson, 2012; Robson, Pitt, & Berthon, 2015); education, particularly for counselling (Bodenhorn & Starkey, 2005; Bayne & Jangha, 2016; Romanelli, Tishby, & Moran, 2017), medical interviewing (Shochet, King, Levine, Clever, & Wright, 2013; Gunderman, 2016), and sales (Rocco & Whalen, 2014); social work (Todd, 2012); and therapy (Sheesley, Pfeffer, & Barish, 2016; Bega, et al., 2016; Wong, 2013). The spirit of applied improv is everyday life and ordinary people, which stems from one key idea in improv: anyone can improvise if they take the time to unlock their creative potential by “re-educating” themselves with new preconceptions, attitudes, and skills. This re-education is what distinguishes improv comedians from others in the performing arts, and applied improv sees the value of that re-education in non-performance contexts like those previously described. Applied improv has largely been driven by improvisers themselves, although psychologists have collaborated extensively as well.

Psychological research on improv as such has found a definitive center in applied improv, and very little research on improv or improvisers themselves exists otherwise. A psychological theory of improv has begun to take shape (Bermant, 2013), which research on applied improv has extended (Bayne & Jangha, 2016; Sheesley, Pfeffer, & Barish, 2016). The primary objective of theoretical inquiry on improv in psychology has been to relate improv to established constructs in psychology—including empathy, unconditional positive regard, and play, among others—that might be leveraged in improv-based clinical interventions. Beyond applied improv and theoretical research, improv has been studied with fMRI (Amir & Biederman, 2016) as part of a larger neuroimaging literature on creativity that includes studies on originality, aesthetics, improvised music, art, poetry, and writing. This literature has the potential to inform emergent theoretical constructs in applied improv as similarities and differences of brain activity between improv and other creative activities are elucidated.

Improv Comedians in Psychology

Unfortunately, the studies of comedians referenced earlier (Greengross & Miller, 2009; Ando, Claridge, & Clark, 2014; Stewart & Thompson, 2015; Stewart, Wiley, McDermott, & Thompson, 2016) have made no direct contribution to the study of improv comedians. Because these studies have been interested to describe comedians’ health in terms of a functional relationship between health dimensions (i.e. personality, longevity) and comedic expertise, conventional measures of expertise have been factored into their study designs that preclude direct observation of improv comedians. For idiomatic reasons that have been described, “elite” must be understood by researchers in a broader

sense than fame and popular appeal if elite improv comedians are to meet the inclusion criteria for studies of elite comedians in general. Nonetheless, these studies are precedent for some challenging inferences about improv comedians: it is possible that elite improv comedians reap the benefits of participating in comedy without the stress of commercial fame, which would seem to fit with the positive spirit of applied improv; but if elite improv comedians are like other elite comedians, then the basic premises of applied improv may require significant revision. Even so, the historical differences between improv and other forms of comedy are substantial enough to assume that there may be some merit to the claims of applied improv; so, how might professional improvisers differ from other comedians in terms of personal wellbeing?

The aim of the present investigation was to formulate thematic descriptions of meaningful experiences of wellbeing among professional improv comedians and illuminate the psychological vulnerabilities and resiliencies of this unique population, providing more nuanced, interpretable data on them than has so far been produced in the literature. Nuance is a decidedly lacking quality in current research on comedians, so this investigation presents a valuable reference for navigating the complexities of mental health research on comedians in the future. The thematic descriptions developed in this research give a voice to improv comedians themselves in psychological research, and also permit the empirical evaluation of current psychological theories of improv comedy. This is of particular benefit for practitioners in applied improv seeking to improve, refine, and systematize their craft, and may also promote self-reflection and improved wellbeing among improvisers. The present investigation also begins to bring together a dedicated empirical literature on comedians in general that, at present, exists only in disjointed form in the tangential interests of disparate research disciplines.

Method

Psychological research on comedians comes with a set of unique challenges for which qualitative methods are particularly well-suited; for this reason, this investigation takes an existential-phenomenological design as outlined by Colaizzi (1978), Polkinghorne (1989), and Osborne (1990). The most significant challenge has already been alluded to, which is that regarding the narrow scope of operational definitions in quantitative research on comedy: conflating traditional measures of success like fame with comedic expertise precludes the study of comedians' experiences in forms of comedy that are less amenable to fame. Furthermore, the very assumption that the study of comedic expertise or success indicates anything peculiar about the effects of comedy on the individual is a faulty one; for example, it is impossible to discern from longevity studies of elite comedians (Stewart & Thompson, 2015; Stewart, Wiley, McDermott, & Thompson, 2016) exactly why this population in particular has a decreased life expectancy—presumably, a greater experience of comedy (as indicated by

elite comedians' comedic expertise) has an adverse effect on comedians' health, but these findings may as easily be explained in terms of the adverse effects of fame and media attention on celebrities in general. Similarly, it would be an error to assume that comedians' higher than average scores on measures of psychotic personality traits (Ando, Claridge, & Clark, 2014) necessarily indicate that comedic ability is facilitated by some degree of psychoticism; rather, these traits may represent successful comedians' adaptations to the unique demands and stresses of pursuing fame in the comedy industry. Without further detail and insight, which is not currently available in empirical research, quantitative studies can only present crude statistics with poor interpretability. By contrast, qualitative methods can elucidate the nuances of existing statistical research and stimulate further inquiries that are more finely tuned to the actual experiences of comedians.

Qualitative research is not merely a supplement for quantitative research in the study of comedians: numbers cannot articulate the qualities of comedians' unique experiences and cognitive processes (and it is precisely these that make comedians such intriguing individuals), but comedians themselves can. Existential-phenomenological research in particular purposes to faithfully and empirically represent the experiences of individuals; as Colaizzi articulates, "*objectivity is fidelity to phenomena,*" so the existential-phenomenologist approaches human science with a posture of respectful listening to what phenomenal experience speaks about itself (1978, p. 52). Being in the tradition of descriptive science, existential-phenomenological psychology is not interested to produce explanatory laws, but rather the ontological understanding of human experience (what it is to be human). The person is understood to be "already existing coconstitutionally with his/her world," an "interdependent unity" that contrasts starkly with subject-object dualism and so implies that persons cannot be understood separately from their experiences of their worlds (Osborne, 1990, p. 80). Consequently, persons' experiences are seen as objectively real, existentially relevant, and necessary for understanding human psychology (Colaizzi, 1978). The experiencing person then is the one who is best suited to articulate the meanings of their experiences (MacKnee, 2002). In taking an existential-phenomenological approach, the present investigation allowed the contributors, or "co-researchers," to describe their experiences of wellbeing and define the meaning of these experiences in relation to their involvement with improv comedy.

Contributors

A total of 8 individuals (5 men and 3 women) participated in this study, recruited by social media (i.e. Facebook, Instagram), word of mouth, and from the researcher's professional contacts in the Vancouver improv community. Inclusion criteria were that participants be: (a) professional improv comedians, as indicated by a minimum one year of regular performing; (b) currently active in the Vancouver area, as indicated by association with at least one Vancouver-

based improv theatre; (c) minimum 19 years of age; and (d) able to articulate his or her experience.

The mean age of participants was 35, with a range of 21. A variety of marital statuses were represented: one participant was single, three were in long term committed relationships, three were married (including common law), and one was divorced. Every individual had completed high school, and six had completed additional education at the undergraduate level, with the highest level of education completed being one individual's Masters degree. Three participants identified with a religious tradition—two Christian and one Catholic—although two of these individuals identified as non-practicing. The other five individuals did not adhere to any particular faith or religious tradition, all identifying instead as agnostic, but with varying expressions of atheism or spiritual inclination.

The mean length of professional involvement with improv comedy was 9 years, with a range of 24. Every participant described involvement with at least three improv companies over the course of their training and professional career in improv, with a mean of 5.5 and a range of 9. Participants described affiliations with a variety of improv companies in Vancouver and elsewhere, the most commonly cited being Vancouver TheatreSports League (7), Instant Theatre (5), The Fictionals (5), and Blind Tiger (3). Every participant was affiliated with at least one of these four companies, but an additional 14 other companies and/or regular shows in the Vancouver area—including Queerprov, Little Mountain Improv, and the now-defunct Second Storey Theatre—had representation in the collective experience of the participants. Lastly, three participants described involvement with improv abroad, citing an additional seven companies—including Second City (2) and ImprovOlympic (2) in Chicago—and cruise ship contracts.

Procedure

Existential-phenomenological methodology recognizes the immediacy of the interview as the most direct means by which to accomplish its aims (Colaizzi, 1978; Polkinghorne, 1989; Osborne, 1990). The contributors were engaged in dialogue about the content and meaning of their experiences, and themes emerged from the narratives they presented. The role of the researcher in this process was acknowledged and accounted for prior to data collection through “bracketing,” in which the researcher rigorously identifies and suspends any preconceptions and biases they may hold regarding the subject matter (see Appendix). All interviews were conducted either in-person or via Skype/FaceTime, and began by briefly familiarizing the contributors with the nature and process of the study. During this time, issues of confidentiality and the contributors' rights as voluntary participants were addressed, and a rapport was established. Once consent was given, contributors were asked to respond to a brief verbal survey of demographic information. Interviews then proceeded for a length of 60 to 90 minutes and were audio-recorded for transcription and thematic analysis. The interviews were structured around two questions: (1) Please describe as fully as

you can your experience as a professional improviser. What has this been like for you? (2) How does your experience as an improviser relate to the experience of wellbeing in your life? The researcher engaged with the contributors as they described their experiences with active listening, empathy, probes, and open-ended prompts (i.e. What was it like to do improv when you first started, and what is it like now? What does wellbeing look like for you, and in what ways does improv contribute to your experience of it?) to help contributors clarify their responses, as well as explore and define the meaning of their experiences.

Data Analysis

The data analysis procedure organized the information provided by the co-researchers into a series of meaningful themes that combine to articulate the common structure of the experience of wellbeing among improv comedians. Phenomenological interpretation of the data followed the descriptive methods detailed by Colaizzi (1978), Polkinghorne (1989), and Osborne (1990), and modelled by Hunnisett (1986) and MacKnee (2002). The steps were as follows:

1. Analysis was preceded by a thorough reading of the transcribed data from each participant in order to acquire a feeling for it.
2. Significant statements or phrases that pertain to improvisers' experiences of wellbeing were extracted from the data.
3. To "spell out the meaning" of each statement the researcher formulated a concise re-representation of each statement.
4. The re-representations were then aggregated into clusters of themes that reach across the barriers of individual experience, cross-referenced with the original data for validation.
5. An exhaustive description of the themes extracted from the protocols was produced, supported by pertinent direct quotations and examples from individuals.
6. This exhaustive structure was refined into a concise, common story that describes the phenomenon's *fundamental structure*.
7. The fundamental structure was proposed to the contributors in a final validating step, and any relevant feedback was worked into the final thematic description.

Reliability and Validity

Reliability in existential-phenomenological research is achieved when researchers can agree on the representativeness of the generated constructs, and was attended to in the present investigation through the involvement of an outside independent qualitative researcher, following the example of MacKnee (2002). This researcher was asked to review a random sample of the significant statements extracted from the data and compare them to the final identified themes. The aim was to attain intersubjective agreement of over 75%, which was successful.

Existential-phenomenological research relies on empathic validity, or the extent to which the researcher's observations reflect the phenomenon of interest, to support its claims. Empathic validity of the generated constructs has been determined in this research by proposing an initial draft of the fundamental structure to the contributors with the request that they compare it to their lived experiences to assess whether these have been faithfully represented by the researcher's interpretations. The thematic descriptions and fundamental structure were then adjusted to reflect the feedback offered by the contributors. The ultimate test of empathic validity in this research is how well these results resonate with all professional improvisers, both individually and as a collective whole.

Results

As the contributors explored the relationship between improv and wellbeing in their lives, a series of seven themes emerged that described their common experience. These thematic categories are not necessarily equally representative of each contributor's experiences since each contributor was able to articulate certain themes with more fullness and clarity than others, so the salience of themes differs from one contributor to the next. Nonetheless, the data analysis identified these themes as standard in each participant's experience.

The results of this research are presented here in three configurations: first, the clusters of themes are described briefly and provided in list format; second, the exhaustive description of themes is given with supporting quotations from the contributors (pseudonyms have been substituted for all names out of respect for the contributors); third, the fundamental structure or common story, which is the aggregate of the participants' combined experiences, is presented to conclude this presentation of the data.

Clusters of Themes

The seven themes that emerged have been divided into two overarching categories: direct/growth effects (6) and indirect/career challenges (1). The direct/growth effects category describes positive changes in personal wellbeing that the participants attributed directly to learning and performing improv. The indirect/career challenges category describes indirect, non-improv career factors (i.e. factors external to the experiences of learning and performing improv) that can contribute to fatigue and burnout among professional improvisers. The exhaustive description of themes also includes some discussion of how the contributors navigate these career challenges to evade or reduce their effects. The themes that comprise the first category ought to be understood as mostly co-occurring and mutually facilitative; however, to accommodate the strictly linear nature of communication, they have been disentangled and arranged in a sequence that attempts to parse their unfolding together, with more foundational experiences being listed first.

Brief Thematic Description of the Experience of Wellbeing Among Improvisers

The seven themes and their categories are listed below. Several subthemes have been included with each theme as well to ensure that the experiences they indicate are fully defined. The themes are as follows:

A. Direct/Growth Effects

1. Opportunity for adults to play and escape constructively
 - i. Freedom to laugh, have fun, relax, and be silly
 - ii. Helps focus attention on being in the moment
 - iii. An oasis that is free from consequence
 - iv. Activity that is inherently satisfying, fulfilling and joyful
 - v. Work that doesn't feel like work
2. Comfort with risk, leaning into vulnerability
 - i. Mistakes are gifts and opportunities
 - ii. Attacks worries about being wrong or looking stupid
 - iii. Challenges fearfulness, perfectionism, and insecurities
 - iv. Liberates one from the idea that life has a script
 - v. Encourages one to embrace the uncertain and "just try"
3. Discovering the joy of collaborative relationships
 - i. Ready access to supportive community
 - ii. Sense of belonging to a team
 - iii. Safe space fosters respect and trust (other people are a safety net)
 - iv. Encourages curiosity in and value for others
 - v. Encourages a generous relationship style with a giving- or support-bias
 - vi. Collaborative spirit unites individuals across differences
4. Improves confidence
 - i. Facilitates mastery experiences
 - ii. Promotes self-acceptance
 - iii. Combats shyness
 - iv. Induces positive personality change
5. Constructive mindset promotes positivity
 - i. Encourages building on each other's ideas ("Yes and")
 - ii. Sensitivity to blocking ("Yes but") behaviors and negative interactional patterns
 - iii. Promotes positive reframes
 - iv. Encourages openness to experience, following new ideas, and personal growth
6. Nourishes emotional health, self-image, and sense of purpose

- i. Performing is emotionally refueling and re-energizing
- ii. Cathartic emotional release for both performers and audiences
- iii. Affirmation from live audience’s immediate feedback
- iv. Mitigates—but does not fix—struggles with mental health (i.e. depression, anxiety, ADHD)

B. Indirect/Career Challenges

- 7. Fatigue and burnout from outside pressures and stress
 - i. Strain from production responsibilities and bottom-line concerns
 - ii. No guarantee of monetary compensation for your work
 - iii. Inter-group politics create hoops and barriers for outside performers

Exhaustive Thematic Description of the Experience of Wellbeing Among Improvisers

A. Direct/growth effects

This category of themes describes positive changes in personal wellbeing that the participants attributed directly to learning and performing improv. These themes appeared with remarkable consistency between contributors and seemed to present in the contributors’ earliest encounters with improv and develop over time, for which reason they have been labeled “growth” effects. Contributors tended to interpret negative experiences with improv within larger patterns of personal growth, so these also have representation here. The contributors own words have been used to define and describe these themes where appropriate.

1. Opportunity for adults to play and escape constructively. Improv is an opportunity to play, to momentarily let go and escape, that adulthood rarely affords. Such opportunities seem to disappear during the transition from childhood to adulthood, but the need for them does not necessarily diminish: as responsibilities increase, so does stress, and at some point that stress needs to be released. Improv directly addresses this need by providing adults with a space in which they can feel free to laugh, have fun, relax, and be silly. As Elaine puts it, “improv is a place where you’re given permission to play.” Such places are few and far between for adults and, when they are discovered, the experience is deeply freeing. Improv also helps one to be mindful of the present, to narrow one’s attention and fully tune into the moment and what is happening in it without introducing past or future oriented concerns. This allows the improv environment to be experienced as an oasis in which one’s only task is to relax and play, free of worry. Jim describes, “anytime I’ve gone through a breakup, I’ve found improv to just be a beautiful escape... some real kind of oasis from the weird ups and downs of my life.” Jack likewise found this to be the case during his divorce:

The moment I set foot on stage is when I get to play, and all of the other stuff disappears... the only solace I had during that shitty,

shitty period was doing shows. I can't think about any of that other stuff when I'm on stage. I just have to think about what did my scene partner just say, and how do we build on that, and we get to be wizards [laughing].

For Jack, improv was a welcome escape amidst the relational conflict he was embroiled in. Improv took on a similar, and much needed role for Michael soon after his mother passed away:

It was quite young to lose a parent. Around that time a friend of mine invited me to a random improv meet up on Craigslist and, for whatever reason, I said, "sure" ... my life was shook to the point that I was needing some kind of artistic, creative escape, and going to those first meet ups and then going to rehearsals, it just felt freeing. It felt more like an hour and a half or two hours where I could just play, versus just worrying.

Improv was an outlet where, for a defined amount of time every week, Michael could allow himself to experience the release he desperately needed and be fully absorbed in the moment.

Improv can have this absorbing quality even in the midst of grieving because it is a joyful, inherently satisfying activity, an end in itself rather than merely a distraction. Ryan discusses this aspect of improv by comparing it to children's play:

If I could sum up in a few words what it is I really love about improv is that we don't play as adults in the sense that we apply to children. When you watch children play it's so open and honest, it's so joyful... usually we think of play as a form of exercise or serious competition, but that's not the way you see kids playing tag. There's no winner in tag. Tag just keeps going until it has to stop, and they enjoy it nonetheless.

As Ryan indicates, children do not play to achieve anything; rather, they play because they enjoy playing, an attribute which in his experience is generally lacking in the major forms of culturally sanctioned play that adults can engage with. What is remarkable is that the inherent satisfaction that can be derived from improv does not diminish when it is turned into a career. As Erin explains, "when it comes down to it, no one's paying us. We're doing it because we want to do it. We're doing it because we love to do it." Money is simply not the motivating factor. Even for those contributors who are fortunate enough to be paid to do improv, it is not about money. As Rachel puts it, "There are moments on stage where you say to yourself, 'I can't believe I'm getting paid to do this' ... it doesn't feel like work, it truly feels like an extension of who I am."

The fact that she gets paid to play simply does not feel real: improv is work that doesn't feel like work because it aligns so well with who she is. The opportunity to be paid to do improv simply means that she gets to do more of this activity

that she loves since her time is no longer divided between improv and full-time work somewhere else. Ryan summarizes the experience neatly:

There are people who are still doing improv professionally and performing well into their 50s and 60s, people who have families and still find time to do it. They're not doing it because there's fame and fortune in improv. They're not doing it because they're making any real money in it. They're doing it because of that feeling, how much they love it, and how much they love that feeling of playing with each other. That is a feeling I don't think we find in too many other aspects of our adult life and they've found it—I've found it—and why would we want to lose that?

Improv remains an enterprise that is enduringly fulfilling, joyful, fun, creative, and playful.

2. Comfort with risk, leaning into vulnerability. Being routinely placed in situations of uncertainty on stage transforms fearfulness into a comfort with risk, a leaning into vulnerability, that extends beyond improv into everyday life. This process is rooted in and facilitated by one of the core principles of improv, the understanding that mistakes are gifts and opportunities. Since there is no script in improv there is nothing to dictate exactly which choices are the correct ones, and so there is really no such thing as a mistake in improv. What may be perceived as mistakes then—a line that just slips out, an action that doesn't really make any sense—can all be catalysts for great moments on stage. Jim articulates how this translates off stage in his experience:

The beautiful life lesson that improv gives you is that there's no such thing as a mistake. We all walk around in our lives so tense about fucking up and about defending someone or saying the wrong thing or doing the wrong thing and it paralyzes us. If we look at [mistakes] as little gifts, then we stop being paralyzed by our fear of screwing up.

A world of possibilities opens up when mistakes are stripped of their threat. Learning to interpret mistakes more positively takes power away from the fear of failure. As Ryan notices, learning improv is “not so much gaining a new skill as un-learning the idea that you don't want to be wrong, you don't want to be stupid, you don't want to say the wrong thing. It's freeing.” This mindset has powerful effects if it is embraced in everyday life as well, as Jack discovered:

As an actor and as a person, I just always wanted to be right or get it right, and if I wasn't going to get it right then I didn't want to bother doing it. Improv gave me the gift of failure and that *failure was okay*. Then when the power gets taken out of failing—just a big word for humanity—there's so much freedom on the other side of that that I didn't realize was there. It was the opposite of everything that was ingrained in me by my family and by my socio-economic situation.

Learning to be okay with failing and appearing stupid was completely counter-intuitive, yet incredibly liberating.

Adopting this mindset pushes one to lean into vulnerability and use the full range of one's resources, challenging inhibiting character traits like fearfulness, perfectionism, and insecurity. Tom describes how improv forced him to reevaluate personal patterns that were hindering him on stage:

We can have someone go through an experience that a player has gone through in their personal life and see how it plays out, whether it's true to life or not, and just have something honest come up on stage... I realized that in order for me to get to that place where I'm comfortable making this very cathartic, connective piece of work, I have to let go of some baggage, I have to feel freer on stage.

Noticing content in scenes that was emotionally triggering provided an impetus for him to begin examining these areas in his personal life. By tracking his responses to triggers on stage and following up on them privately and with a counselor, he eventually gained new comfort with that subject matter. Analogous uses of an improv-life feedback loop empower individuals to embrace risk in a plethora of other forms. Ryan finds uncertainty is one such risk that has lost its intimidating character since he became acquainted with the improv mindset. He notes that while some have gone so far as to describe his actions as courageous, he's "really just as scared as them, but know[s] it's better to try it." Once again, a world of possibilities opens up when the potential for failure is stripped of its threat.

3. Discovering the joy of collaborative relationships. The freedom to make mistakes is facilitated and experientially learned through what Erin describes as the "inherently collaborative practice" of improv. The improv environment is an invitation to experience and contribute to interactions with others that are free of judgment, criticism, and defensiveness, to open oneself up to the possibility and joy of building collaborative relationships. Respect, trust, and support are given in the improv community, regardless of whether any two people have ever met each other. Michael puts it this way: "being an improviser means that you automatically have a built-in improv family in different cities." His idea is elaborated by Erin's experience of the same phenomenon:

Once you step onto a stage with someone, even if you're not part of the same company, you know that you're going to say yes to what they give you and you know that you're going to give the best offers you can to the people on the stage. That really translates off stage in most cases as well, so for the most part it makes for a really lovely place to be.

The collaborative, group-oriented process that unfolds on stage translates into analogous habits off stage, from which emerges a generally accessible supportiveness that ranks among the defining characteristics of the improv community.

Many of the contributors described improv as a “team sport.” The role of the team in improv is to assume the function of cheering on and affirming the individual’s freedom to explore without fear of being seen as stupid, unintelligent, or unworthy. As Jack describes it, “you are there to build this safety net that creates an environment that people can create in without censoring themselves.” This safety net is the responsibility of each team member, and one of the most powerful, yet delicate elements of the entire improv experience. Erin describes what it was like to play with a team mate who did not commit to supporting her:

You need to feel able to fail and to know that your team mates are going to stick with you, but with this player I never felt that and so it made improv very scary... If you go in with without any respect for your scene partner, or afraid of what they might say, then you’re going to have really shitty improv ... improv is a team sport. It’s about relationships and a group mind sort of thing. If you have any one person off doing their own thing, you don’t trust that you can pass the puck to them and you’re probably going to lose because you can’t rely on your teammate.

It only takes one person to make the safety net fall apart, but improv only succeeds when the whole team fully commits to their role in it. The fact that success on-stage is contingent in this way upon maintaining a sense of safety between performers impacts relationships off stage as well. As Jim describes, “you’re only as good as you are when you’re hanging out, waiting to go on stage, and if I’m not making my scene partner look good there, then they won’t want to play with me anymore.” Improv simply does not reward egotism, whether on stage or off; rather, it consistently reinforces esteem for others and a bias for generous, giving, and supportive relational skills.

The efficacy of improv’s relational framework is perhaps nowhere more apparent than when people are united in the pursuit of common goals in scenes, despite coming from radically different backgrounds in real life or holding potentially incompatible convictions. Jim offers an example from an improv class he taught in which one student’s free speech convictions sparked a conflict with a few classmates who identified using the pronoun they/them:

He says “well I look around the room and I don’t think we’re going to have any they/them problems here,” but then two students say, “uh, yah we are”... cut to three weeks later, they’re playing in scenes together and completely supportive of each other. You can’t do improv unless you on some level like the person you’re doing improv with, you just can’t. When you truly allow yourself to make mistakes, screw up, and look like a fool in front of each other, you can’t help but start to like the other person more.

Jim was able to observe a powerful uniting experience unfold for these students. Improv has similarly shaped Rachel’s own perception of others: “I think improv

has helped me find the things that make us the same... there are more things that we have in common than set us apart at our core.” This understanding allows her to connect better with a more diverse range of people, as personal differences which may otherwise have seemed insurmountable become opportunities for curiosity and exploration. Jack echoes much the same sentiment when he says:

There’s more common ground than we’re currently finding in the world, where we’re more and more divided. Not that [improv] is the savior of all that, but I think it sure helps to get a new group, take a class with 11 strangers, and say yes and for an hour.

This uniquely powerful, transformative space for connecting with others is surely among the greatest gifts that improv has to offer.

4. Improves confidence. Enough time spent becoming comfortable with failure in front of supportive others pays dividends for one’s confidence overall. Confidence should be distinguished here from comfort with risk, in that confidence is understood to pertain more to a stable component of personality than to situational courage: whereas courage is the capacity to manage fearfulness, confidence is the quality of being less fearful. These experiences are mutually facilitative, in that conquering fears makes them less frightening, which opens up the possibility of conquering new and greater fears.

Improv facilitates this process of developing long-term confidence first and foremost through the extensive opportunities it provides to gain mastery experiences. Erin describes what learning improv was like at first for her:

Even though I wasn’t always volunteering to do scenes, I loved the collaboration aspect. I loved being able to spend time in the presence of people that I considered really talented improvisers, and I knew that if I stuck around eventually I would feel comfortable.

Putting in the time to become comfortable volunteering for scenes was an experience of overcoming for her, after which she could go on to readily perform in front of audiences and do shows with greater artistic challenges and complexity. That which challenged her initially is not what challenges her now. Jim’s first experiences with improv were not in a class setting, but on stage in front of an audience in a bar after being brought there by a friend:

My buddy really bullied me to go on stage there, and the first time I went I was terrible. Second time I went, I was a little bit less terrible, but I started to like it. Third time I went, I was okay, just starting to learn how to do some of the games—it was all bar-prov, so it was all drunk people there having a good time, but I was learning on the fly, learning while doing shows. I didn’t really know how to do the game styles, I maybe wasn’t funny, but I at least knew how to make interesting choices and continue the storytelling.

Seeing progress with each attempt provided him with the sense that he was

mastering something, allowing the sense of risk to slowly disappear each time he stepped on stage. He describes that from his vantage point now, “some people say, ‘wow, that’s so hard what you do!’ but no, it’s easy for me because I’ve done it for years... it’s like how you don’t get nervous when you drive anymore.” When a fear is challenged enough times and finally overcome, it does not need to be overcome again.

Another avenue through which improv develops confidence is self-acceptance. Improv directly challenges the fears that one is not likeable, not funny, or not good enough through its cardinal principle, “*yes, and.*” The essence of “yes, and” is unconditional acceptance of what one’s scene partner has to offer (saying “yes”), and a willingness to enter into and build on what they have to offer (the “and”). Michael describes what this has meant for him off stage: “Improv is all about ‘yes, and-ing,’ acceptance. I think improv has allowed me to accept myself. All of my glories and my tragedies.” For “yes, and” to work, it must be reciprocated by everyone on stage, which means that eventually one’s own ideas must be met with unconditional acceptance and support; recognizing this reveals just how loud one’s inner critic is, and assists in the process of learning that one’s ideas—and by extension, oneself—are indeed worthy of acceptance. Tom noticed how improv helped him come to this realization:

I grew up in a pretty conservative Christian family, and as I discovered that I was attracted to men it created a lot of conflicting feelings. There was a lot of self-loathing and non-self-acceptance that came out of that. Over time I started to realize how, even after I was out, even in my other relationships, I had a lot of trouble with authenticity and self-acceptance. It was a weird process of noticing signals of that in improv scenes but then also noticing in my personal life that, “oh, I’m having a lot of trouble listening to what this person is saying,” respecting what they’re asking for.

Learning to listen to and respect the other on stage ultimately forced Tom to look inward and begin learning to listen to and respect himself, to value and esteem all that he had to offer. This personal growth was cued by patterns unfolding in his improv; however, Tom adds that, “I honestly think that curbing those habits involved just as much personal work on myself (often with a trusted counsellor) as it involved going to improv classes and being on stage.” The truth that Tom has revealed here is an important one to note: improv is often more catalyst than cure, and does not promise a free pass on the hard work of personal growth and self-care.

Over time, however, learning to both thrive in once-terrifying situations and accept oneself can certainly lead to significant personality change and growth. Some of the contributors described how improv had combatted long-standing patterns of shyness in their lives. Elaine articulates how she experienced this in her life:

Improv definitely allows me to be better at parties! Being a pretty

severe introvert, parties and social interactions tend to be the worst, really. I think improv allows me to not be so overwhelmed as I would have been in the past, just having conversations with strangers, so to me it's been really life changing. I don't even know what I would be doing really.

Social situations which were once debilitating have lost their threat for her. As she describes, "I just roll with things, I don't worry, I don't hyper focus on the stakes and I don't worry about things as much as I used to." Improv has allowed her to worry less overall, to be less fearful, and engage with the various aspects of her life more freely. Jim similarly notices a range of personality traits that improv has impacted in his life:

Finding improv has been probably one of the best things I ever did. I mean it's completely changed my personality. It's made me more outgoing, it's made me more confident, it's made me a better listener, it's been made me a better teammate and I think it's made me a better collaborator. It's made me more patient, it's allowed me to check my ego. And had I known that there was an activity or a skill set that I could learn that was going to teach me all of those things, or give me all of those gifts, I would have done it immediately... We're teaching ourselves how to actually behave in real life when we're learning how to improvise.

As Jim describes, the growth that improv stimulates in one's personality is extensive. The personal resources he has developed through improv, these "gifts," all combine to help him meet the demands of his life without fear, without defensiveness, without the need to assert or force himself unduly on situations. This is what confidence is, and its impact on wellbeing is immensely positive. As Erin summarizes, "I would not be the confident and happy person that I am without improv."

5. Constructive mindset promotes positivity. Enough time spent practicing "yes, and" internalizes the principle as a way of living; the corresponding mindset is fundamentally constructive, rather than critical, which in turn cultivates a positive disposition toward others and the future. Jim cogently articulates the contiguity of the "yes, and" principle on stage and off:

My conversations have become better in the last 10 years because in an improv scene, I've got to 'yes, and,' I've got to throw more information into the scene so that [my scene partner] has something to react to, and so I do that in my regular life. I never respond with "oh, I'm doing fine"—I say "oh, I'm doing fine, *and* I've been eating a lot of avocado lately, who knew?" or something. Then that's allowing someone into the conversation with me, because that's how I would do it in an improv scene."

Jim recognizes that the perfectly civil response—"I'm doing fine"—still lacks

something, still ends the conversation, even though it acknowledges and accepts the validity of the question being asked; because he is disposed by his improv training to not just say “yes,” but to say “yes, and,” his everyday interactions are characterized by the same constructive approach he practices on stage. Positivity is the emergent quality that defines relationships conducted in this manner: it is impossible to be constructive when one is tearing things down, so unlearning the destructive, critical response naturally attunes one to the positive in every situation, rather than the negative. This has been particularly transformative for Ryan:

With my improv friends we’re not negative with each other, because it doesn’t help anybody. We’re positive with each other, constantly, so interacting with anyone else ever in life, when people say and do things I react positively because they like it, it helps them.

The constructive, positive way of relating to others that he has learned in improv has enriched the way he engages with others, even in his most everyday encounters.

Included in this constructive mindset is a sensitivity to the blocking, or “yes, but” behaviors that underlie negative interactional patterns. As Elaine observes, the “yes, and” language has provided her with a framework for understanding why any given interaction in everyday life succeeds or falls apart:

One of the things I observe a lot of is blocking. We talk about simply starting scenes with positive energy, positive choices, really listening and accepting. I found when I was working with people that have a drug or alcohol dependency how much they “yes, but” everything, how much they block other ideas. Even when I was doing counselling or group work, I think “okay, they’ve given me an offer”—it’s either a verbal offer or a non-verbal offer—“are they listening to my offer back? Oh, they’re blocking it, they’re ‘yes, butting’ it.” I’m listening predominantly in terms of that language.

The improv language allows her to gauge the receptiveness of others, their willingness to engage in and build something together in the moment. Every interaction involves a reciprocal process of give and take, and improv provides a framework for understanding where blockages might be occurring in this process. Rachel describes how a similar process unfolds for her:

There are moments where I use an old habit of thinking, and I catch myself before I open my mouth and say, “what if I just give someone the benefit of the doubt? What if I take a breath and let them finish? And what if I respond to only what they’re saying and don’t say what I’m pre-loading in my mind?” I would say it’s not taken away conflict entirely in my life, but it’s helped me to manage relationships differently.

Improv has allowed her to adjust her habitual pattern of responding and reframe

her negative responses in conversations more generously, taking ownership of the attentiveness and accuracy of her listening and of being positive in what she gives back. The latter point was touched on by Elaine as well, and Erin articulates it quite effectively when she says, “there needs to be as much emphasis on creating offers that people want to say yes to, in your life and on stage, as much as there is an expectation and encouragement to say yes.” The “yes, and” principle ultimately implies a holistic transformation of the way in which one conducts oneself, demanding thoughtfulness both in how one receives and what one gives.

When the “yes, and” principle takes root as a way of being, the hallmarks are an openness to experience, a willingness to follow new, even foreign ideas, and be open to one’s potential for growth. Tom describes how he finds these qualities are transmuted from improv to everyday life:

In improv, there are so many situations where you hear someone else’s idea and realize that it only makes things more difficult to decide that there’s no way it’s going to work, that it’s probably going to fail. Finding the space in myself to realize that, I may not get it at first, but if I go with it a little longer, then maybe we’ll get somewhere that I could never have gotten on my own—that’s so analogous to life. We all have our limited perspectives and skills, and the only way that we can overcome those limitations is by acknowledging that other people have other things to offer.

Being open to what others have to offer, regardless of whether their offering has any obvious merit, and recognizing the limits of what one can accomplish alone are absolutely vital concepts both for improv and for living. Elaine likewise finds that, “when I am really using that improv mindset—saying yes, being open, supportive, lifting people up—is when I’m happiest, when I’m actually doing improv in real life.” There is clearly much to be gained from embracing the constructiveness and positivity of the improv mindset in everyday life.

6. Nourishes emotional health, self-image, and sense of purpose. Improv has a nourishing effect on mental health and wellbeing: it helps sustain emotional health, bolsters self-image, and contributes to an ongoing sense of purpose. These benefits belong to the realm of the day-to-day and, like drinking enough water or getting enough exercise, are accessible insofar as improv is regularly incorporated into day-to-day life. The consensus was unilateral with respect to the energizing effects of performing shows. As Ryan describes, “it’s a big thrill entertaining people and making people laugh, just in some way giving them joy. Ever since I was a kid I’ve loved getting that reaction, I just love performing.” Elaine corroborates the sentiment when she says, “there isn’t a feeling in the world like doing a sold out show on a Saturday night and seeing the audience bent over, killing themselves laughing—it’s magic.” Michael references mobile gaming to define the addictive quality of the experience:

The reason why mobile games are so addictive is because they give

you little rewards every day or every hour. Improv is addictive for me because, when I put on a good show and there's a nice audience, or when I post a photo afterward and it gets 10 likes, that's a reward. When the players say that they had a fun show, that's a reward. And those little hits of happiness keep me going.

Performances are regular doses of happiness, joy, excitement, and stimulation that are emotionally revitalizing. Jack expresses the same idea, but from a different angle:

Improv gave me laughter. It gave me, not a fake positivity, but a levity and a sense of humor that wasn't based on the misfortune of others, that was just witty and fun. And I'm surrounded by other people who are witty and fun.

Jack here emphasizes being situated in a positive environment where he gets to laugh regularly, in which he is continually in the company of people who make him laugh. Rachel articulates her experience in a similar way, "I get to laugh a lot. Like genuinely laugh and be constantly, genuinely surprised by my colleagues and by people I work with or teach." This is not to say that a periodic break from improv cannot have its benefits, as Jim describes: "I'm not so addicted that I can't appreciate time away from it, but then you really come to appreciate what it is, what it offers... it's such a big adrenaline dump, I really think I'd miss it." These are all just variations on a theme: live improvised performance is a rejuvenating, emotionally replenishing experience, like fuel in a tank.

Improv is cathartic as well, providing an avenue for emotional release. As Jack notices, "there's something so cathartic and healing about laughing every day, and now I get to bring that to people on a regular basis. I get to bring it to every aspect of my life." Jim similarly hones in on the shared element of the experience with an audience:

There could be someone in the crowd that's just had a miserable day or a miserable week or a miserable month, and this is that time when they're actually allowed to laugh, and I see it. I'll look out there and I'll see people just losing their minds. People go to rock shows or sad movies for similar reasons—they get to feel their emotions with a bunch of other people and society has said "yes, it's okay." It's super cathartic, and I get to be a part of that everyday. I get to be a sort of conduit for people to let their emotions out, and I get to let my own emotions out a little bit too. I need it, you know? It's my favorite thing to do. I think it keeps me engaged in the world in a way that not everybody has.

The experience of simultaneously facilitating and participating in this kind of cathartic release with an audience is deeply satisfying, and the more it is incorporated into one's everyday routine the more difficult it is to go without

it. The audience-performer dynamic factors similarly into Rachel's day-to-day wellbeing, backing up her decision to pursue a performance-based career:

I need to perform, I need to be in front of people, I need to have that feedback... You give a lot when you're in front of an audience, and you take a lot from an audience too, but it's led me to live a very authentic life. I feel like this is really what I was meant to do.

What she invests of herself in each audience is reciprocated in their feedback, their laughter, which affirms the value of her investment in them and contributes significantly to her sense of purpose overall. For Michael, "improv has shown me that I am someone who other people enjoy, which is very important to remember when one is going through depression." The experience of making an audience laugh can materially refute distorted self-perceptions and buoy self-image.

Even so, improv is no miracle cure for mental health: the consensus was unanimous that improv mitigates, but does not fix, key mental health struggles such as depression, anxiety, and ADHD. Mental health is a puzzle composed of an immense number of pieces, and even if improv accounts for a large number of them, it does not account for the whole picture. Tom's caution for artists is to become more aware of "the benefits of focusing on their mental health through counselling, self-education, and self-inquiry before going 'all-in' to the arts with an assumption that their art will make them feel better." Improv may be therapeutic, but it is not a one-for-one substitute for therapy. Michael expresses much the same sentiment:

Improv is one part of my wellbeing, but it's not the be all and end all of making me be a happier person. I think that's work that never stops and I think that's work that has so many other pieces that I haven't even found yet... Improv definitely makes one happy, but I don't think it's the key to happiness.

Nonetheless, improv has its piece in the puzzle, as Erin's experience with anxiety, depression, and ADHD illustrates quite poignantly:

Mental health is a big priority in improv. Improv has really supported me in my anxiety and my depression. I still have really high highs and really low lows, but having something that I love, that includes other people, and that I can pour myself into and be filled up in return is so important. I have depression, anxiety, and ADHD, and that can serve me really well in improv and it can really screw me over... I know when my ADHD is screwing something up for me, when my brain is turning something bad or I've forgotten something, but just to have a place where my ADHD is not a disadvantage means that, in the places where it is a disadvantage, even if it's still a problem, it's easier to look past, it's easier to forgive myself, because I know that sometimes it is a strength. I'm not cured. I have ADHD and I'm going to have that for my whole life, and that can

be a huge pain in the ass. But at least I have somewhere that, even if it isn't an advantage, it's not a disadvantage.

Improv is clearly a vital component of her wellbeing, regardless of the fact that it has not done away with her problems. As she concludes, “If I didn't have improv in my life, if I wasn't able to spend as much time as I am blessed to spend on it right now, I would not be happy. My mental health and emotional health would be garbage.” The nourishing effect of improv on mental and emotional health, not to mention self-image, is a powerful combatant in the ongoing struggle to maintain mental health and wellbeing.

B. Indirect/career challenges

This category of themes describes challenges that emerge alongside, yet outside the experiences of learning and performing improv, and that can contribute to fatigue and burnout among professional improvisers. These appeared to be standard challenges faced by all the contributors in the process of making a career out of improv. The greatest variance in overall wellbeing among the contributors seemed to be attributable to this category of themes, so the aim here is to elucidate the common challenges underlying this variance. Some effort is also made to comment on the comparative effectiveness of different strategies for managing these challenges. The contributors own words have been used where appropriate.

7. Fatigue and burnout from outside pressures and stress. For all the benefits they reap from practicing their craft, fatigue and burnout do occur among professional improvisers. The contributors, however, mostly attributed this to the pressures and stresses of those non-improv realities which necessarily accompany a career in improv—what some describe as the “business” and “bureaucracy” of improv—which is consistent with the preceding discussion regarding the inherently satisfying and emotionally nourishing qualities of improv.

Without question, the most prominent example raised was the strain of production responsibilities, especially bottom-line concerns. Tom's summary of the issue is quite apt, although it has not personally affected him: “there are so many improvisers and improv teachers who do it for a good chunk of their living... it's more survival focused, they have to balance doing something creative with making ends meet.” However rewarding improv may be, depending on it for one's financial security makes it incredibly difficult to reap its benefits. This is the reality for Michael, who runs an improv company that is successful enough to cover his bills, but small enough to make the economic consequences of a poor turnout or bad show weigh quite heavily upon him. This can make it virtually impossible at times for him to engage with improv as play, to see it as “work that doesn't feel like work,” since the sense of being free to fail on stage is hindered by the awareness of what is at stake business-wise. Michael expresses it this way:

Improv now is work and this work has consequences, because audiences pay a little bit to come and watch us, conventions book us to come and perform, performers come to practice and perform their craft on stage, the venues need to make money from our nights so we need to have an audience there to buy food... I think when I find a place to do improv that has no consequence, I'm just going to smile. When it's with the right group of people, the right audience, and in a place and time where I don't need to worry about anything except for actually playing and improvising, I can almost guarantee to myself that I would be so much happier.

As Michael so clearly articulates, the problem is not that production responsibilities limit the fun of improv (after all, it can be reasonably assumed that improvisers who do not derive some “fun” or artistic satisfaction from producing shows do not typically become producers), but rather that they introduce a sense of consequence to improv that is ultimately toxic to the improv mindset, particularly the inter-performer safety net. For this reason, much is to be gained by disentangling production responsibilities from improv. Larger improv companies, for example, are able to distribute production responsibilities more evenly so that they do not weigh so heavily on any given performer while on stage. This allows Erin to keep a certain distance between her company's production concerns and her performing:

Sometimes after a townhall meeting with our cast, things can feel a little bleak and scary. It's like your parents sitting you down and saying, “look Dad lost his job” ... but the only thing you can do to help is keep performing and keep bringing people out to shows. It's really nice that the thing we can do most to help the company is to keep doing what we're doing and to do it more and to do it better.

Because the fate of the company is shared by more than just her, she is able to narrow the scope of her concerns to include only what is actually under her control—her performing. For Michael, he has to create opportunities for himself to focus on performing in this way:

I prefer performing improv on a stage that is not mine. It's like going over to a friend's house to play—you can be a little more silly, a little more loose, you're not going to get in trouble if something weird happens—but when you're at home you have to be a little more responsible.

Performing with other companies allows him to get out from under the weight of his “producer hat,” as he referred to it, to breathe and just play.

The other major contributor to fatigue and burnout among improvisers is that few improvisers are guaranteed pay for their work, as Ryan indicates: “improv doesn't usually pay, but sometimes it does, in terms of we once in a while get grocery money.” This is the reality for most improvisers, and most of the contributors—Ryan included—have to maintain other, often full-time work.

This does not always create problems, as Jim describes: “I make half my income through improv and half my income through the other job, so neither one is my sole source of income. I never really look at improv as being a kind of financial cash cow.” Rachel echoes this thought when she says, “if I didn’t get paid or improv didn’t pay me enough, then I do have other work as well to supplement. I don’t think anything really will change, but I am extremely privileged to get paid.” Both Jim and Rachel are fortunate to make enough money from improv that it can form part of their incomes, and if either income stream were to fall through then they have the other to fall back on. Some of the contributors are not able to form a substantial part of their income from improv, but the hustle to do shows and make a career out of improv does not change. As Erin describes: “I probably spend 40 hours a week on improv and improv related activities, but it does not pay the bills... I think the most difficult thing is primarily the financial aspect.” Improv does not leave her much room to fit other work into her schedule to allow her to cover her bills, which makes time a precious commodity for her. This hustle is worthwhile for her since it allows her to do improv as much as possible, but it is nonetheless exhausting.

Finally, inter-group politics can create obstacles for outside performers to become involved with new groups. This challenge was most prominent in Ryan’s experience, who recognized that it was at least partly based in the fact that improv does not typically yield a high financial return, as discussed previously. As he puts it, “how do you keep a company afloat that puts on shows and teaches? It has to get money where it can, but coming as an outsider, there are a lot of hoops you have to jump through, that bureaucracy.” He goes on to describe some of the particular hoops he has had to jump through:

You would want to go do stuff with one of these companies but they they say, “well okay, you have to take these classes” and I would say “well I’ve already taken these classes” and they’d say “yah, but not with us.” So after 4 years of doing improv, doing private gigs, being paid to do improv, and even teaching improv, I have had to take Intro to Improv and pay money for it at three separate companies because they won’t let you take the advanced classes until you’ve taken their intro class, and they won’t even consider putting you in a show... it’s a little frustrating, and sometimes these ground rules seem like less of a professional thing and more of a “that’s how they make money” thing.

Ryan’s persistence is quite remarkable, since many would-be improvisers are completely derailed by experiences like his. As Elaine has observed over the years:

I’ll see really great people get taken out by the politics and the competitiveness of professional improv. I think that it’s sort of the un-fun realities of business or politics and all that kind of stuff gets into their soul and makes them bitter and takes them out. Really, you’re there to please the audience, for your own development, and

to *play*. If you focus on the reasons why you love it so much, it still feels like home, and there isn't a feeling in the world like it.

The crucible of improv politics and bureaucracy can be difficult to withstand, but it is certainly worthwhile for those who do.

The Fundamental Structure

Although there were some individual differences in the experiences shared by the eight professional improvisers who were interviewed for this study, a fundamental structure or common story emerged from what was described. The goals of this research were to discover the common ground between the participants' respective experiences with improv, and then how these experiences related to their mental health and wellbeing. Accordingly, the resulting narrative first paints in broad strokes the common progression of the participants' careers in improv, with an eye toward what has changed and stayed the same since their first encounters with the art form, before delving into how their careers presently relate to their personal sense of wellbeing. The seven themes that have so far been described are woven throughout both sections of this narrative.

It should also be noted that the narrative presented here is arranged in a loosely chronological sequence, but the details of the experiences it describes should not be understood as strictly linear. Many of the described experiences unfold concurrently in real life, layering together and sometimes even mutually facilitating each other in any given moment.

Common Story

Although details varied with regard to how each improviser began their career in improv, there was remarkable congruence in the way that they described encountering improv for the first time. One strong commonality was a powerful experience of laughter. For some, there was a specific moment, either attending an improv show or taking a class, in which they found themselves laughing and simultaneously realizing that they had not laughed so much or so deeply in a very long time. For others, this experience was extended over time, and it was only later that it fully became apparent how much improv had restored laughter to their lives. The opportunity to laugh regularly was profoundly welcome for those who found themselves taking up improv while adjusting to major life changes, especially significant loss of one form or another (the death of a parent, for example). Improv presented itself as an opportunity for worries, concerns, and problems to be suspended for a given amount of time each week. Improv was a regular escape, an oasis, a couple hours set aside to simply laugh, have fun, relax, be silly, be creative, be revitalized, live fully in the moment, and just play. These experiences were further distinguished by the fundamentally collaborative and supportive nature of the environment. The freedom to explore and try new things was grounded in the encouragement of instructors and the receptivity of classmates. Most of the improvisers noted that they have maintained friendships

with many of the people they met in those first classes, whether or not they continued on with improv together. The improv space was one that encouraged vulnerability with others, and in which vulnerability was met with cheering and applause. This was deeply freeing, even needed—in fact, the word “addictive” was offered by many to summarily express this experience.

A further part of what made improv so compelling is that it was as challenging as it was freeing. Some of the participants identified as strongly introverted, so signing up for a class to do what they described as their “worst nightmare” took courage in and of itself. To them, improvisers were heroes, an entirely different kind of human—inhuman even—so they couldn’t possibly imagine themselves ever having the courage to step out on stage and be so completely unafraid and uninhibited. Some felt self-conscious about going to their first improv classes; after all, adults don’t do things so trivial and silly as improv. It felt childish, and some even recalled not wanting their friends to find out about them taking classes. Others coming from some form of performance background found that the successes they expected to have going into their first class did not come as easily as they had thought. Improv dismantled their self-perceptions that were built on false confidence and instead rewarded the hard work of learning to listen to and support others’ ideas, take risks, fail, and look stupid, to not worry about personal image or being the funniest, most talented person in the room. For all, those first improv classes targeted insecurities and faulty preconceptions, but also revealed opportunities to grow and a framework in which to do so. Paradoxically, being challenged in this way contributed to the perception of the experience as liberating, breaking down personal barriers to a more open, authentic life.

The progression into making a career out of improv was largely rooted in the desire to create more opportunities to continue doing improv. Many described the thrill of performing more artistically complex or demanding shows, or developing and executing their own format, and the deep sense of satisfaction that resulted from these achievements. Those who had the opportunity to teach improv described with similar enthusiasm what it was like to see others experience the same benefits that they themselves experienced when learning improv. Since many companies are not able to compensate their performers for their work, some of the participants had other jobs that would allow them to make ends meet while doing as much as 40 hours of improv per week for no pay. Naturally, those participants who were compensated for their work felt extremely lucky, but typically they still had other work to supplement their income and allow them to afford the cost of living. For both groups, money was only motivating insofar as it allowed them to pay their bills and keep doing improv, and any money coming directly from doing improv just made it easier to do more improv. Some of the improvisers remarked that doing improv professionally was not an option they ever considered or even really knew existed, especially since they were inclined to think of work as quite serious whereas improv was anything but. Improv still did not feel like a profession for many since the feeling they have on stage during scenes was the same as the day they started—it still

just felt like play. A number of participants described it as the most fulfilling, positive work they had ever done, and some expressed this sentiment with the phrase “work that doesn’t feel like work.”

Experiences varied surrounding the non-improv realities of being a professional improviser, but a common thread that emerged was that improv thrives when performers feel free to fail and make mistakes, to be vulnerable and open rather than afraid and defensive. When this freedom is threatened is when improv begins to feel stressful and less playful. Larger companies can divide production and administrative responsibilities between more people, but these responsibilities can be attached to as few as one person for smaller companies and independent shows. At this smaller scale, bottom line concerns can have much higher personal consequences—like paying production costs out of pocket if enough tickets aren’t sold—that introduce stress and pressure to performances that would otherwise not exist. Participants who run their own companies noted that it can be quite therapeutic to do improv for other companies since they could focus entirely on the improv in these contexts without worrying about any of the business aspects. Similarly, those who had quite positive experiences with production or administrative roles also had plenty of time on stage to actually do improv, which after all was the very thing that every participant fell in love with in the first place.

Overall, the participants felt that improv continues to be an important component of their personal wellbeing. Improv still provides an opportunity to play and escape for a few hours every week, or every night for some. Many find that being on stage is a cathartic experience and that being able to share that kind of emotional release with both audiences and fellow performers on a regular basis is vital for them. Hearing an audience laugh after a line or seeing them invested in a scene was regarded by all as a thrilling, addictive experience, and for some, this instant access to reactions that only comes with a live audience is particularly energizing in a way that work in film and TV is not. The routine of being a performing improviser and the accompanying feeling of being part of a team—or as some described, an “improv family”—provides many with a sense of belonging and purpose. This was quite important for those who have mental health struggles like anxiety, depression, or ADHD, who noted that while improv is no miracle cure, to have an environment in which they belong, where they are accepted exactly as they are and where their struggles can become strengths, has a notably positive impact on their overall mental health and self-confidence. Those who identified as strongly introverted and shy found themselves significantly less overwhelmed in large social situations or when meeting new people, and some even felt that they became more extroverted and derived more enjoyment from these activities than they once did. Others described how improv has benefited their self-image, or self-acceptance. For example, personal features like body type or skin color do not limit the kinds of characters and roles that one can play: in improv, anyone can be the leading lady or the general of the army, no matter who they are or what they look like. Many find that this also benefits their self-confidence in day-to-day

life and helps them to focus on what they and others have in common, rather than what sets them apart. Some felt that they were now more curious about other people and less interested in themselves, as well as more inclined to see the value in others' differences. Following from this, many also felt that they had become better at collaborating with people with whom they have little in common. They also described how foundational improv principles like “Yes and”—which encourages supporting and building on each others' ideas—have helped them build more positive, upbuilding, and generous relationships with others in all aspects of their lives. Perhaps the most common sentiment that was expressed was that these improvisers learned to see mistakes as “gifts and opportunities.” For all, stepping on stage without a script time and time again has helped them in their everyday lives to be more confident in embracing experiences and ideas with uncertain outcomes, to be more comfortable with taking risks, and to be open to failing, knowing that it will be better to just try something than to do nothing at all.

Discussion

The object of this study was to define the common experience of wellbeing among professional improv comedians. The thematic descriptions yielded by this research respond in particular to two questions anticipated by the existing literature: first, what makes improv comedy special, such that it could lend itself more potently to one's experience of wellbeing than other forms of comedy or art? and second, is it responsible to promise any degree of improvement to one's wellbeing by developing skills in the craft of improv comedy?

Improv as General Promoter of Wellbeing

To begin with the former question, it is clear in the themes yielded by this analysis that the contributors benefit profoundly from practicing their craft. Besides being an inherently satisfying, fulfilling, and joyful activity, improv supplies these individuals with a remarkable confidence and sense of freedom that extends into their everyday lives and combats the paralyzing effects of fearfulness, shyness, anxiety, and perfectionism. From the vantage point of psychology, these benefits strongly resemble established concepts of psychological wellbeing—like play (Erikson, 1943; Bruner, 2000), self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977; 1978; 1982), and especially the characteristic directions of the fully functioning person described by Rogers (1962)—that therapists routinely endeavour to help their clients foster through psychotherapy. Clearly, these are desirable outcomes, and the unique mechanics of improv appear naturally to push improvisers to develop them.

Play

The relationship between improv comedy and psychological theories of play has been established previously by a few authors (Bermant, 2013; Bega, et al., 2016;

Sheesley, Pfeffer, & Barish, 2016), and the salience of playfulness in the thematic descriptions produced by this study further supports that connection. In his studies of play among children, Erikson (1943) found play to be a key component of healthy development through childhood. As he and others developed his theories of play, the importance of play for the child's development was extended to the adult as well. Play assumes a central role in fostering vitality, joy, wonder, creativity, passion, friendship, and more among children, and play therapists endeavor to help adults recover these dimensions through a return to play (Bruner, 2000; Hoare & Erikson, 2002). For the average person, however, the play activities they enjoyed as a child will not inspire the same enthusiasm in their adulthood; just as older children do not play with the toys they enjoyed as infants, adults likewise need play activities that correspond to their changing interests and stages of cognitive development. To this end, improv corresponds in difficulty to the sophistication of its players and in content to their creativity, interests, experience, and knowledge—like a kind of Swiss Army knife, improv really has something for everyone.

But is improv truly special in this regard? To be sure, any other form of comedy can be a joyful, satisfying, even playful pursuit; but as long as there is a script, or a perfect delivery for a given joke or line, then comedians performing stand-up or sketch will continue to run the risk of falling into perfectionism and all the potential anxiety and negativity that follows. In fact, in any prepared performance art (e.g. live theatre, film, television, music), however much one is encouraged to take chances in rehearsal, perfection matters once the performer takes the stage, gets in front of the camera, or sits down in the studio. While mistakes may be handled gracefully by the experts, there will always be the tendency to perceive them as a failure to perfectly deliver the intended performance.

By contrast, the study's contributors emphasized the freedom they felt in improv to make mistakes and see where they go. This freedom is essential to improv at even its highest levels: in improv, mistakes are opportunities, and the most skilled improvisers may be considered experts in making mistakes and running with them to create moments that simply do not arise through strict intention. The closest analogue to this in another established art form is probably musical improvisation, especially in jazz (which especially is tuned to the principle of "no wrong notes"). But to improvise in music one must be wise to the language of music, of harmony, scales, and the operation of instruments; to improvise in comedy, only the skills of everyday life and ordinary conversation are truly required, and with a little imagination one need not (indeed *should* not) think twice about it. This is perhaps how improv most uniquely parallels children's play: when children play, there are no prerequisite skills, and no pressure to "get it right"—they just play.

Social Learning

Can improv's environment of play be modelled to identify exactly how it may be fostering dimensions of wellbeing among participants? Perhaps the most plausible explanation of this interaction may be drawn within Bandura's (1978) social learning theory, in which the self-system is analyzed according to reciprocal interactions between cognition, behavior, and environmental events. This model, referred to as reciprocal determinism, construes the self dynamically, and so is well suited to account for the contributors' stories of personal growth, many of which involve the challenging of fundamental self-beliefs.

Upon reaching adulthood, many adults have developed a very static self-perception. There are qualities that they believe are fundamental to their identity, and changing those qualities is not possible (one might consider one's own self-beliefs about confidence, intelligence, attractiveness, popularity, etc.). Improv, however, encourages the development of a flexible self-concept and the use of imagination to inhabit identities and social roles one may not normally (if ever) occupy. Furthermore, no expectation is ever passed to the performer to be a plausible fit for the role they assume—executives, janitors, romantic leads, villains, sidekicks, knights, damsels, even animals or inanimate objects are all performed regularly by improvisers of all body types, genders, ethnicities, and backgrounds to equal effect. This phenomenon should sound familiar, as it is precisely the experience of children playing make-believe: in make-believe, a child is free to be anything they can dream of, but at some point they reach adulthood and the freedom of make-believe ends; perhaps their grades weren't good enough, or their family didn't have enough money, or that critical promotion was given to someone else, but one way or another the boundless possibility of make-believe is boarded up and that ex-child settles into what adult life is apparently going to be. For any adult that can empathize with this feeling, an improv class can feel like tearing those boards off and being a child again for a short time. By encouraging adults to “play make-believe,” improv can facilitate a re-structuring of hindering cognitions (faulty self-beliefs, expectations, negativity, etc.) and reopen an adult's mind to the possibilities of who, what, and how they can be in a variety of situations.

Self-Efficacy

Far from simple escapism, however, such cathartic experiences can help adults re-structure their self-beliefs and yield personal changes they may never have thought possible. Consider the contributor Elaine, whose self-belief regarding her shyness and introversion prevented her from functioning comfortably at parties or in the classroom—indeed, in her words, she would have once described such environments as “paralyzing” or “debilitating.” The environment she was immersed in through her first improv classes, however, profoundly challenged her expectations of what would happen if she stepped out of her shell and looked (in her opinion) silly in front of others; today, she routinely and comfortably performs on stage in front of entire audiences with no need to shy away from looking

silly. What happened? In short, her self-belief that she would be received poorly by others if she acted a certain way caused her to behave in a shy manner to avoid the undesired consequences she anticipated. But the improv class allowed her to test her hypothesis and see that it was false; after all, she could in fact stand in front of a group of people, do something outlandish, and be received positively. From this point she was able to set progressively higher goals until she was finally comfortable enough to perform on stage, the prospect of which would have previously crippled her with anxiety.

Social Learning Theory would frame examples like Elaine's in terms of self-efficacy: an individual's persisting in and mastering subjectively threatening activities in the improv classroom leads to increased self-efficacy and lower defensiveness regarding those behaviors in the future (Bandura, 1977). Furthermore, these attainments in the classroom form a basis for building efficacy in those activities outside of the classroom, leading to increased confidence in more spheres of the individual's life.

Group Cohesiveness

What is it that makes the individual comfortable enough in the improv classroom to undertake a subjectively threatening activity in the first place? The key ingredient here is Rogers' (1957) most famous concept, unconditional positive regard (UPR). This concept is introduced in improv settings under other names—phrases like “positive feedback,” or being “nonjudgmental” or “non-critical” of scene partners, were commonly used by the contributors—but the idea is unequivocally the same. Rogers defined UPR as the absence of “*conditions of acceptance*,” removed completely from any selective evaluation of another's behavior or character; it is a “prizing” of the whole person, their best and their worst, and a caring for them as separate and unique from oneself (1957, p. 98). Yalom and Leszcz (2005) developed the idea of UPR in group therapy and recast it as *group cohesiveness*, describing how when a group of people is encouraged to adhere to the principle of UPR it creates a therapeutic safety net that fosters unity and togetherness between persons. Research has demonstrated that group cohesiveness is indeed the primary agent in developing collective self-esteem and optimistic expectations of self-improvement, or “hope for the self” (Marmarosh, Holtz, & Schottenbauer, 2005, p. 34). Group cohesiveness as such is—and the point cannot be understated—*essential* for the personal benefits described in this study to be achieved through participation in improv.

Improvisees adhere to the tenets of UPR as part of their craft; many of the contributors alluded to this when discussing the importance of a “generous playing style” both on- and off-stage. First, the improv classroom must be a safe place in which for individuals to learn, experiment, and make mistakes without judgment; it must be a place where individuals can fumble the accents they're working on, blank on responding to scene partners, and forget plot points or character names without being belittled by fellow classmates. When helping one another to think critically about performances and make improvements to their

craft, improvisers must keep feedback constructive and uphold the dignity of the performer, demonstrating that acceptance in the group is not contingent on performance. Even once on stage in front of an audience, this continues to be of paramount importance: in fact, for some of the contributors, it was something of a pre-performance ritual to remind their fellow performers that they have one another's backs; that if one scene partner is floundering, the others will attempt to bail them out rather than leaving them high and dry or lampooning them in front of the audience. After a performance, improvisers must continue to have each other's backs by debriefing shows in a positive, constructive manner. Finally, improvisers must practice acceptance of fellow performers that may differ from themselves in terms of race, culture, gender, sexual orientation, religion, political ideals, popularity, talent, and more.

If improvisers do not practice their craft in this way, it leads to a fracturing of group cohesiveness that is readily apparent to any observer and extremely damaging to the self-esteem of other performers. Some of the contributors described how performing with scene partners that didn't have their backs—perhaps by being harshly critical, playing selfishly, or discriminating against them for personal attributes—could make them feel extremely uncomfortable, anxious, and even unsafe. Furthermore, such behaviors do not translate well in front of an audience; improvisers derive the content of scenes from their collective creativity, and scenes suffer when performers feel unable to contribute or are even actively prevented from contributing by a fellow performer. In a way, this means that improv auto-enforces a generous playing style—i.e. to be the best, one must play generously—but this should not be taken for granted. Improvisers should be vigilant of their own behavior and that of their fellow performers to ensure that abuses, whether on- or off-stage, are addressed and corrected.

In considering how a generous playing style may be maintained by improvisers up to the highest levels of performance, it is helpful to remember that improv is not strictly a form of comedy; rather, at its most basic level, it is about improvising stories. The performers create characters and see what happens when they interact; the scene ends when the story reaches a natural conclusion. The humor is often derived simply from the situations that arise, or small details the performers add to their characters, or the risk of not knowing where a scene is heading. Jokes and punchlines may present themselves, but they are not the backbone of the art form as they are in stand-up and sketch comedy. To be sure, the vast majority of improv is comedic, but working generously with scene partners (paying attention to what they do and say, responding accordingly, not contradicting their choices) can as easily produce content that is comedic as it does content that is dramatic, so a “funny-at-all-costs” attitude may actually hinder an improviser in the end. Once one embraces this aspect of the art form, the pressure to keep an audience laughing diminishes and it becomes easier to spot the potential in ideas others bring to the table, if not for comedy then at least for great storytelling. It is in this way that improvisers are uniquely capable among ensemble performers to embrace one another without conditions

of acceptance, without having to be “good enough.”

The Fully Functioning Person

Altogether, improv appears to promote the general wellbeing of a person in a way that aligns strongly with the characteristic directions of the fully functioning person described by Rogers (1962), who argued that the optimum, “fully functioning” person would be increasingly open to experience, accepting of her becoming a process (“a work in progress”), and have an increasing trust in her own instincts. The goal of therapy in Rogers’ view, insofar as the purpose of therapy is to foster psychological health, is to help individuals move in these directions.

The dynamics of make-believe and group cohesiveness in improv are key factors that contribute to an increasing openness to experience. Make-believe engages the imagination and expands the realms of possibility, allowing one to experience oneself in very different situations and social roles than one may occupy in everyday life; group cohesiveness creates a safe space in which to explore. This expanded world of possibility in play contributes to a less rigid self-concept overall. Too often people cling too tightly to what they believe are the “facts” of their identities, as can be seen in the common assumption, “people can’t change.” In actuality, the only “facts” to be found are in one’s experiences, and one’s identity is sure to prove quite accommodating and dynamic when one allows oneself to be receptive, or open to those experiences.

Gains in self-efficacy, or confidence are the major component in developing the latter two directions of Rogers’ fully functioning person—accepting oneself as a “work in progress” and increasingly trusting in one’s own instincts. As has been established, the self-concept is dynamic, and thus amenable to growth. Opening up to new experiences in the improv classroom, especially those that may be subjectively threatening (perhaps playing a character that is totally opposite from oneself), is a way of acknowledging this room to grow, but persisting in and mastering those experiences is what proves to oneself that one can actualize that growth. Such attainments increase efficacy in those activities and contribute to an overall sense of confidence in oneself, especially one’s ability to tackle further new and challenging activities. In this way, past attainments in the improv classroom can help diminish one’s insecurities and fearfulness, fostering instead the increasing trust in one’s own instincts that Rogers has in mind.

What is of particular importance in Rogers’ conception of the fully functioning person, however, is that she is an optimum, or ideal state toward which individuals can strive, but never fully arrive at. This reality was borne out in the contributors’ experiences as well in the remarkable fact that none expressed the feeling of having run out of things to learn or grow in through improv, even amongst the most seasoned members of the cohort; rather, each contributor demonstrated the commendable desire to continue developing themselves as artists, performers, and people—a phenomenon which at the very least is a

significant step in the direction of psychological health, if not the very definition of it.

Improv as Livelihood

While improv may generally be a potent promoter of wellbeing among improvisers, those who seek to make their livelihood from it may run into challenges that limit the beneficial effects of their craft. The contributors largely described improv as “work that doesn’t feel like work,” but some found this sentiment diminished after experiencing the business of it. Especially in smaller improv companies, financial stresses can easily slide to the forefront. A few bad shows and drops in ticket sales mean lost wages for everyone; however, further out-of-pocket costs may be entailed if a venue’s rental fees can’t be covered by ticket sales. The desire to avoid such financial troubles can allow perfectionism to creep in, influencing expectations for oneself and one’s fellow performers which fundamentally damage the group’s cohesiveness.

Perfectionism is no distant worry for larger companies either though—as a company establishes its reputation and saturates its roster, it is easy for one to begin obsessing over the quality of performances to ensure they continue to meet audience expectations. In either case, it is important for improvisers to stay grounded and keep their reasons for getting involved with improv in the first place front and center; for showrunners in particular, it is important to continue fostering an atmosphere of togetherness and remember that—to paraphrase one contributor—the best thing anyone can do to keep their company afloat is try their best.

Second, it is difficult for the average improviser to make a living doing improv full-time, and those that are lucky enough to do so may still struggle to cover their bills without working extended hours or taking a second job beyond a traditional 40-hour work week. The effects of such extended working hours are well documented in the literature: relationships are known to exist between long working hours and dimensions of physiological ill-health, like cardiovascular disease, hypertension, diabetes, sleep quality, and fatigue (Sparks, 1997; Van Der Hulst, 2003; Knauth, 2007; Bannai & Tamakoshi, 2014; Yamauchi, et al., 2018), as well as impairments to cognitive functions like attention, alertness, reasoning, and decision making (Proctor, White, Robins, Echeverria, & Rocskay, 1996; Virtanen, et al., 2009); overwork can also lead to unhealthy weight gain (Shields, 2000), reduced quality of relationships and family life (Crouter, Bumpus, Head, & McHale, 2001; Fitzgibbons Shafer, Kelly, Buxton, & Berkman, 2018), burnout (Joaquim, et al., 2017), anxiety and depression (Virtanen, Stansfeld, Fuhrer, Ferrie, & Kivimäki, 2012; Bannai & Tamakoshi, 2014; Afonso, Fonseca, & Pires, 2017), and even in some cases suicide (Yoon, Jung, Roh, Seok, & Won, 2015; Yamauchi, Sasaki, Yoshikawa, Matsumoto, & Takahashi, 2018). Somewhat paradoxically, however, a recent study (Kuroda & Yamamoto, 2018) has also demonstrated that reported job satisfaction increases for those working more than 55 hours per week, which the authors suggest may explain why many

individuals choose to overwork themselves in spite of the apparent costs to their physical and mental health. For many improvisers, this may indeed be the case, as the need for adequate rest is trumped by the desire to perform as much and as often as possible at the expense of personal wellbeing. It is important then for improvisers to remember that, as much as improv appears to be “work that doesn’t feel like work,” ordinary rest and a healthy work-life balance maintain a high value in the broader equation of wellbeing.

Improv as Vehicle for Therapy

What challenges, if any, may exist for those wishing to apply improv in clinical contexts? A definitive consensus among those contributors who had experience with clinically diagnosed mental health issues may provide a useful starting point for this question: improv is no miracle cure, but it can be part of the solution, especially if paired with professional help.

Keeping this in mind, improv might best be considered a *vehicle* for therapy, rather than therapy in and of itself. Improv certainly has clinical potential, as apparent in the host of strengths discussed previously, but that potential can easily be missed by participants who don’t know what to look for (which is likely most people). To this end, a trained professional should be involved to guide participants through the therapeutic material. Sheesley, Pfeffer, & Barish (2016) describe a sound model for such a practice, which entails a unique composite of improv and cognitive-behavioural therapy (CBT) designed specifically for participants with social anxiety disorder, run jointly by an improv instructor (the group leader) and a mental health professional. This model, which the authors termed Comedic Improv Therapy (CIT), homes in on dynamics like play and group cohesiveness discussed previously, promoting them from mere by-products of the craft to explicitly intended outcomes. The interplay of the group leader and the mental health professional is a key dimension of CIT, especially so as to facilitate pauses at important junctures in the class to debrief concepts and exercises, ensuring they achieve the greatest impact they can. Leveraged in this way, improv plays an analogous role to the experiential exercises psychotherapists commonly use to help their clients work through difficult material, albeit on a substantially larger scale.

What does an improv-based approach have to offer existing psychotherapies? One could argue that some individuals who are not inclined to seek out traditional forms of psychotherapy may be more willing to seek help in alternative formats. Indeed, there is evidence to show that offering clients a choice between equivalently effective treatment options improves treatment satisfaction, completion, and outcome (Lindhlem, Bennett, Trentacosta, & McLear, 2014). For some, the more embodied, physically active character of an improv-based approach may be quite a bit more compelling than the verbal, expository nature of talk therapy. For others, articulating emotions and other psychological contents may be extraordinarily difficult, but working through them more viscerally with a touch of make-believe may be more manageable. Regardless of why, that some

clients may simply prefer alternatives to traditional modes of psychotherapy is reason enough to explore improv-based approaches.

Still, one could argue further that developing competency in a seemingly tangential activity like improv during therapy provides an opportunity to help the client tell a new story about themselves. One of the contributors described how, upon finding improv, she finally felt like she had found an activity where her ADHD didn't make her feel like she was broken, where the realities she struggled with in the other arenas of her life actually gave her competencies and insights that her fellow improvisers didn't necessarily have. This is an experience that is both deeply therapeutic and especially uncommon for many who struggle with similar realities. In such cases, the goal of improv may not even be to fix the issue, but to show in a powerful way that context determines the goodness or badness of a quality, and at least one context exists in which the quality one has always perceived as a flaw can be transformed into a strength. This makes working on the quality in contexts where it is not so helpful a much smaller task, as one may no longer feel the need to erase the quality completely or feel inferior for possessing it.

Finally, one could do worse than to argue that improv's greatest therapeutic strength is its efficacy in building supportive, trusting relationships. In the practice of psychotherapy, it is commonly acknowledged that the single greatest determinant of effective practice is the working alliance, which is to say the supportive relationship developed between client and practitioner (Rogers, 1957; Bordin, 1979; Horvath & Symonds, 1991; Yalom & Leszcz, 2005; Horvath, Del Re, Flückiger, & Symonds, 2011; Fisher, Atzil-Slonim, Bar-Kalifa, Rafaeli, & Peri, 2016; Cheng, Lo, & Womack, 2019). The avenues through which improv fosters a safe, supportive space need no further discussion, but it is important to note that this, above all else, is the critical foundation on which any clinical application of improv should be grounded.

Conclusions

Altogether, the improvisers in this study paint an impressive picture of the personal benefits of practicing their craft, so it is little wonder why there has been such interest in recent years in leveraging those benefits for the purposes of therapy. Consideration of the potential challenges that can befall career improvisers reveals, as may be expected, that there are of course limits to what improv can achieve for one's overall wellbeing, but such consideration does little to expose any hidden flaws inherent to the craft itself that could hinder wellness later on. Indeed, career length appeared to have no impact on enthusiasm for the craft and its personal benefits as communicated by the contributors, suggesting that those positive effects are not merely associated with a kind of honeymoon phase, but last with improvisers over the course of their careers if they are careful to avoid overwork, burnout, or other career factors. Now while everyone may not be suited to the life of a career improviser, it certainly seems that, in the end, a little bit of improv can go a long way for anyone.

Limitations

Being descriptive in nature, this research does not attempt to generate explanatory laws that functionally relate wellbeing with improv, but rather purports to define the meaning of individuals' experiences of wellbeing in relation to improv. Although the final themes produced by this research were validated by the contributors, faults of memory and the inadequacy of language may impact self-reports. Replication of the study may account for such faults, and otherwise refine, extend, revise, or validate the thematic description of the phenomenon's fundamental structure. Generalizability of the outcomes is limited to improv comedians who have been involved with improv professionally for at least one year. Explorations of this phenomenon with co-researchers of different ages, genders, education levels, ethnicities, and lengths of professional history with improv could add new dimensions to the findings. Also, the present research limited its scope to improv comedians presently active in Vancouver, BC, but regional differences in how improv is performed, taught, and practiced at different theatres could affect the generalizability of this investigation's themes for improvisers outside of the Vancouver improv community's sphere of influence. Ultimately, readers and others who have experienced a relationship between improv and wellbeing in their daily lives will be the judges of whether the interpretations of this research are supported.

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Appendix

Bracketing

Although this inquiry is conducted through a psychological lens, the impetus behind the questions it asks is my personal experience as an improviser. I became acquainted with improv comedy in my first year of university and performed improv for the first time in front of an audience that same year. I have performed improv regularly with my university's improv troupe for five years, and have performed improv semi-professionally in downtown Vancouver for three of those years. I was hired by the university in my fourth year there to teach improv for a one-year term, during which I drafted and implemented a curriculum for teaching the fundamentals of improv.

My involvement with improv comedy in university, however, was not the first expression of my love for improvised performance; in fact, my deep interest in improvisation originated with music. I have always had a preference for playing music by ear, rather than using formal notation. I felt constrained by the material assigned in my piano lessons, but derived immense satisfaction from what I could create spontaneously with the piano. I took up music in earnest when I decided to teach myself guitar, which I learned by way of trial and error, relying heavily upon improvisation to discover sounds and musical ideas that I found appealing. I made a major breakthrough as a musician when I encountered jazz in high school and learned that improvisation could be an end in itself. Improvisation was no longer merely a means for creating new, replicable material; rather, the moment of spontaneity had a meaningful existence in and of itself, and its value was not commuted to it through replication. I was drawn to the wonder and magic of improvisation, to the immediacy of expression, or the freedom, that it offered me.

I became involved with improv comedy in the first week of my undergraduate education at Trinity Western University. I had become aware of the university's resident improv troupe, 11:07, as a high school student, and I had hoped to try it out when I began attending the school. My involvement with musical theatre in high school had shown me that, while I enjoyed theatrical performing and being on stage, acting from a script was both constraining and anxiety-inducing for me. Improv comedy, by contrast, appealed to the same sensibilities I had been developing as a musician. I immediately fell in love with improv comedy after attending the first 11:07 workshop of the semester, and I became a regular at those weekly workshops for the rest of the year. I was cast in one show that year, and the next year I was a regular cast member, performing in almost every show. That second year of improv, however, culminated in a great deal of anxiety, stress, and frustration for me, as my lack of formal training had left me with few tools to analyze and understand what I was doing on stage; put another way, I couldn't understand why the audiences laughed when they did, and what I could do to improve my performances and increase my consistency as a performer.

I had the opportunity to take a class at Vancouver TheatreSports League (VTSL) with some friends from 11:07 at the end of that school year, which completely changed my perspective on improv. I learned to let go of a lot of baggage that I was carrying onto the stage, and this newfound sense of personal freedom carried over into my everyday life. I continued taking classes at VTSL over the course of that next year, and I continued to both grow as a performer and experience immense personal benefits from what I was learning there.

In one of my classes, I met a classmate whose sole purpose for taking classes at VTSL was because it was “better than therapy.” As a psychology student, this shook my view of therapy, but as an improviser it radically expanded my understanding of what improv could be. I took on the role of coordinator at 11:07 in my fourth year of university, during which improv and psychology became more intimately connected in my perspective than ever before. I was beginning to adapt basic concepts from Rogerian theory (particularly unconditional positive regard, but also more basic foundational skills like awareness, grounding, and centering) for warm-ups in the workshops I was leading, inspired by similar practices in my VTSL classes. My efforts to help my improvisers be more honest, genuine, and grounded before stepping on stage had a notably positive effect on the quality of our shows, and on the atmosphere of our improv community at 11:07. During this time, I also became aware of improvisers whose regular attendance at 11:07 workshops was being encouraged by their counsellors. It was impossible for me to ignore the fact that improv was having an incredibly positive impact on many of the people that I knew.

The present research sprang from my personal reflections on the existence of The Second City’s *Improv for Anxiety* class. This program seemed incredibly intuitive to me, given the remarkable benefits of improv that I had observed in my own career with improv, but it also piqued my curiosity as to the limits of improv. How much benefit can improv have? Surely, improv alone could not be the solution to Miss America’s passion for “world peace” (although there is a certain satisfaction to imagining people all over the earth opening United Nations care packages to find DVD box sets of *Whose Line Is It Anyway?*). I figured that improv must have limits in its capacity for enhancing an individual’s wellbeing—it cannot be some miracle cure to be taken and swallowed like a pill. Thus it is my aim in the present research programme to determine how much good improv does for those who do it the most, and what the limits of that good are. I imagine the benefits of this research extend to both the improv community itself and the various practices of applied improv.